

ANALYSIS OF A HYBRID HEATING SYSTEM BASED ON HEAT PUMPS AND SOLAR COLLECTORS

Abdukarimov Bekzod¹, Urishev Omadjon², Islomov Davlatbek³, Ikromov Solijon⁴

^{1,2}PhD, Associate Professors of Fergana State Technical University,

^{3,4}Master students of Fergana State Technical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20770803>

Abstract. *This study presents a comprehensive analysis of hybrid heating systems integrating solar collectors and air-source heat pumps. The research investigates direct expansion (DX-S-ASHP), series indirect expansion (IDX-S-ASHP), and parallel IDX-S-ASHP configurations, with particular focus on a proposed hybrid IDX-SAHP system using vacuum tube solar collectors and a plate heat exchanger. The proposed configuration provides hydraulic independence between the solar collector and heat pump loops, improving thermal stability and operational reliability under variable climatic conditions. Thermodynamic and energy efficiency analyses demonstrated that the proposed system can increase the coefficient of performance (COP) from approximately 3.06 in conventional air-source heat pump systems to about 5.21. In addition, electricity consumption was reduced by nearly 70% due to effective solar thermal utilization and thermal energy storage integration. The results confirm that hybrid solar-assisted heat pump systems can significantly improve building energy efficiency, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and support sustainable low-carbon heating technologies for modern energy-efficient buildings.*

Keywords: *Heat pump, Vacuum tube solar collector, IDX-SAHP, Plate heat exchanger, Energy efficiency, COP.*

1. Introduction.

At present, reducing energy consumption in the building sector, improving the efficiency of heat supply, and decreasing harmful emissions into the atmosphere are among the most pressing scientific and practical challenges. The building and construction sector accounts for a significant share of global energy demand and contributes substantially to energy-related carbon dioxide emissions. In particular, in 2022, the building sector was responsible for 34% of global energy demand and 37% of CO₂ emissions associated with energy and industrial processes. Therefore, the decarbonization of building heating systems and the implementation of technologies based on renewable energy sources are considered key priorities [1].

Heat pumps are regarded as one of the most promising technologies for building heating. According to the International Energy Agency, heat pumps, when powered by low-carbon electricity, represent a central technology for the transition to sustainable and secure heating systems. Moreover, replacing fossil fuel-based boilers with heat pumps reduces greenhouse gas emissions even under the current electricity generation mix, and this advantage increases as the power sector becomes greener. According to IEA estimates, space heating alone accounts for approximately 4 Gt of CO₂ emissions annually, highlighting the urgent need to adopt efficient technologies in this field [2].

In cold-climate countries (Northern Europe, Canada), solutions for efficient operation of heat pumps at low ambient temperatures were developed in the 1990s and 2000s, including two-

stage cycles, intermediate heat exchangers, and vapor injection techniques. These innovations helped overcome the major drawback of air-source heat pumps—performance degradation under extremely low temperatures. By the late 2000s, heat pumps had firmly established their position in the heating sector of new buildings in many developed countries. The experience of Switzerland illustrates this trend: despite having a well-developed gas distribution network, approximately 75% of newly constructed detached houses in the early 2010s were equipped with heat pump heating systems [6]. By 2010, several million heat pumps of various types had been installed across Europe, with annual growth rates ranging from 10% to 20%.

Literature review.

One of the indicators of the growing interest of the scientific community in heat pumps is the number of publications. While in the 1990s the Russian-language literature featured an average of 5-15 publications per year, this number increased significantly in the 2000s and peaked around 2010-2011. Figure 1 illustrates the dynamics of publication activity on heat pumps in Russia/CIS from 1970 to 2020. A clear acceleration is observed after 2000, corresponding to the described stage of development.

Figure 1. Dynamics of the number of publications on heat pumps based on a bibliographic review (1970-2020). A sharp increase in interest in this topic was observed after 2000, reaching its peak in 2010-2011 (CIS countries) [3].

At the same time, the use of solar energy in heat supply systems has significant potential. The application of solar thermal collectors reduces fuel consumption, enables partial or substantial coverage of heat production through renewable sources, and improves the overall energy performance of buildings. Recent review studies indicate that building-integrated solar technologies, including solar thermal systems, play an important role in enhancing energy efficiency and reducing environmental impact. However, since the efficiency of solar collectors depends on weather conditions and solar radiation levels, their standalone application does not always ensure a stable heat supply [4].

From this perspective, hybrid heating systems based on heat pumps and solar collectors are of particular scientific interest. In such systems, solar energy serves as a low- or medium-temperature heat source, while the heat pump upgrades this heat to a useful level and meets the building's heating demand. Recent scientific reviews demonstrate that integrating solar technologies, heat pumps, and thermal energy storage systems can reduce building energy consumption, improve the system's coefficient of performance (COP), and accelerate the transition to low-carbon heating. Furthermore, contemporary research on solar-assisted heat pump systems increasingly focuses on their application under various climatic conditions, as well as on optimization and control strategies for these systems [5].

Systems integrating solar energy with air-source heat pumps represent one of the most promising directions in modern energy-efficient heating technologies. Such systems combine the renewable and environmentally friendly nature of solar energy with the high energy efficiency of air-source heat pumps. As a result, the overall coefficient of performance (COP) of the system increases, electricity consumption decreases, and the reliability of heat supply improves [6, 7]. The drawbacks associated with the intermittent operation of solar collectors and the reduced efficiency of air-source heat pumps under low ambient temperatures are effectively mitigated through hybrid integration schemes [8].

Solar-assisted air-source heat pump systems are generally classified according to their configuration into direct expansion systems (DX-S-ASHP) and indirect expansion systems (IDX-S-ASHP) [6, 9]. Indirect expansion systems, in turn, can operate in either series or parallel configurations. Each configuration is suited to specific climatic and load conditions, and they differ in terms of energy efficiency, reliability, and structural complexity [10].

1. DX-S-ASHP system. In the DX-S-ASHP system, the functions of the solar collector and the evaporator are integrated. In this configuration, the refrigerant directly absorbs heat within the solar collector and undergoes the evaporation process at the same location. This arrangement reduces intermediate heat exchange losses and simplifies system operation [4, 6]. Under solar radiation conditions, the temperature of the collector-evaporator surface increases, which improves the refrigerant evaporation conditions and reduces the compressor workload [11].

Figure 2. Schematic of the DX-S-ASHP system.

The main advantage of the DX-S-ASHP system is its simplicity and high heat transfer efficiency. This is because solar energy is directly transferred to the refrigerant of the heat pump. However, this configuration is highly dependent on external solar radiation. When solar radiation decreases or during cloudy weather conditions, the system performance may decline [9, 12]. Therefore, the DX-S-ASHP system is considered more effective in regions with relatively high solar resources.

Studies show that structural improvements in the evaporator and collector significantly affect the overall performance of the DX-S-ASHP system (Figure 2). For example, the use of finned solar evaporators, dual-source evaporators, or combined solar-air evaporator configurations has led to a noticeable increase in the COP value of the system [11-13]. Thus, although the DX-S-ASHP system has a simple structure, its efficient operation largely depends on the optimization of the evaporator-collector section [6].

Main characteristics of the DX-S-ASHP system. Table 1

Parameter	Description
-----------	-------------

Connection Type	Direct expansion
Main Feature	Solar collector and evaporator are integrated
Advantage	Low intermediate heat losses, simple structure
Disadvantage	Strongly dependent on solar radiation
Application Condition	Regions with high solar resources
Efficiency Factor	Highly dependent on the collector-evaporator design

As can be seen from Table 1, although the DX-S-ASHP system has a relatively simple structure, its stable operation is closely dependent on environmental conditions and solar radiation. Therefore, in designing this system, the collector area, refrigerant type, and evaporator design play an important role [9, 11].

2. IDX-S-ASHP Series System. In the IDX-S-ASHP series system, the solar collector and the heat pump evaporator are separated from each other. The heat obtained from the solar collector is first stored in a thermal storage tank or transferred through an intermediate heat carrier, and then delivered to the evaporator of the heat pump [10]. This configuration is particularly useful in cold climate conditions, as the heat obtained from solar energy increases the evaporation temperature and improves the efficiency of the heat pump [14, 15].

Figure 3. Schematic of the IDX-S-ASHP series system.

In the series connection scheme, solar energy is first collected and then used as the heat source for the heat pump. As a result, even under conditions of weak solar radiation, a certain level of stable heat transfer can be maintained through the thermal storage tank [10]. This is especially important in winter when the outdoor air temperature is low. Under such conditions, the standalone performance of an air-source heat pump decreases, while the series solar connection helps to mitigate this drawback [15]. The advantage of the series configuration is that it allows more effective utilization of solar energy and creates more favorable operating conditions for the evaporator at low temperatures. However, due to the presence of an additional thermal storage tank and an intermediate heat transfer loop in the system, its structure becomes more complex and the initial investment cost is higher [10, 15].

Main characteristics of the IDX-S-ASHP series system. Table 2

Parameter	Description
Connection Type	Indirect expansion, series
Main Feature	Solar heat is first stored in a thermal storage tank
Advantage	Increases evaporation temperature under cold conditions
Disadvantage	More complex system, requires more equipment
Application	Cold climates with solar availability but low ambient temperatures

Condition	
Efficiency Factor	Depends on the size and control of the thermal storage tank

According to the data in Table 2, the series IDX-S-ASHP system operates particularly efficiently during the winter season. In this case, the heat obtained from the solar collector provides a more favorable heat source for the evaporator and improves the performance of the heat pump [13, 15].

3. Parallel IDX-S-ASHP System. In the parallel IDX-S-ASHP system-an indirect solar-assisted air-source heat pump configuration-the solar collector and the air-source heat pump operate relatively independently. Both sources can supply the consumer load either simultaneously or separately, depending on demand [10]. When solar energy is sufficient, the collector covers a large portion of the heat load, whereas when solar energy decreases, the ASHP operates as the primary heat source [16].

Figure 4. Schematic of the Parallel IDX-S-ASHP system.

The main advantage of the parallel configuration is its flexibility. In this setup, the solar collector and the heat pump are not tightly coupled. Therefore, the system can adapt more quickly to sunny, cloudy, or variable weather conditions [16, 17]. During summer and transitional seasons, parallel systems often demonstrate higher efficiency, as solar energy covers the majority of the load and the operating time of the heat pump is reduced [17]. However, in parallel systems, it is important to properly control the interaction between the collector and the heat pump. An improperly selected control strategy may lead to increased energy consumption. Therefore, intelligent control, load forecasting, and parameter optimization are of great importance in parallel systems [16, 18].

Main characteristics of the Parallel IDX-S-ASHP system. Table 3

Parameter	Description
Connection Type	Indirect expansion, parallel
Main Feature	Solar collector and ASHP operate independently or together
Advantage	High flexibility and easier control
Disadvantage	Energy consumption may increase without optimal control
Application Condition	Moderate climates with variable weather conditions
Efficiency Factor	Depends on control strategy and load distribution

As can be seen from Table 3, the parallel IDX-S-ASHP system has high flexibility and can operate efficiently under variable weather conditions. In particular, when solar energy and the air source are used alternately or simultaneously, the energy efficiency of the system increases [16-18]. **Comparison of connection schemes.** When selecting among the three

configurations mentioned above, it is necessary to consider the climatic conditions of the region, solar resources, heat load, and economic factors.

Table 4. Comparative characteristics of DX-S-ASHP, series IDX-S-ASHP, and parallel IDX-S-ASHP systems

System Type	Main Advantage	Main Disadvantage	Effective Application Conditions
DX-S ASHP	Simple structure, low heat losses	Highly dependent on solar radiation	Regions with high solar resources
Series IDX-S-ASHP	Effective in cold conditions	More complex construction	Cold and sunny regions
Parallel IDX-S-ASHP	Flexible operation	Requires optimized control	Variable weather conditions

The DX-S-ASHP system stands out for its simplicity and low intermediate heat losses, but it is more dependent on solar radiation [9]. The series IDX-S-ASHP system is more suitable for cold climates and improves the performance of the heat pump under low-temperature conditions [14]. The parallel IDX-S-ASHP system, on the other hand, offers high flexibility and allows the use of solar energy and air sources alternately [16].

2. Materials and Methods

According to Table 4, each connection scheme is more effective under certain conditions. Therefore, when designing a hybrid heating system, it is advisable to select a technical solution that matches the climate, energy source, and load characteristics, rather than relying on a single universal configuration [6, 10].

Figure 5. Fundamental hydraulic connection scheme of the indirect solar-assisted heat pump (IDX-SAHP) system integrated with solar collectors.

Figure 5 illustrates a combined heating and cooling system consisting of solar water heaters, a heat pump, a heat exchanger, a thermal storage tank, and fan-coil units. The proposed hydraulic connection scheme represents an indirectly integrated (IDX) hybrid system that combines solar energy and heat pump technologies into a unified thermal energy supply configuration. The operating process of the system begins with the heating of the working fluid inside vacuum tube solar collectors under solar radiation. The generated thermal energy is then transferred through a central plate heat exchanger to the heat pump circuit. Such a technical solution hydraulically separates the collector loop from the heat pump loop while simultaneously increasing the evaporator temperature of the heat pump under low ambient temperature conditions. As a result, compressor electricity consumption is reduced and the overall operational stability of the system is improved. The thermal storage tank integrated into the system performs the function of storing excess thermal energy accumulated during daytime operation and stabilizing the building heating load throughout the day. The stored energy is finally distributed inside the building through a parallel fan-coil network by convection heat transfer, ensuring rapid and uniform indoor heating performance. The practical implementation of the proposed system allows maximum utilization of solar energy resources, significantly increases

2.1. System description

The proposed hybrid heating system is based on the integration of vacuum tube solar collectors and an air-source heat pump through an indirect expansion solar-assisted heat pump (IDX-SAHP) configuration. The system consists of solar collectors, a plate heat exchanger, a thermal storage tank, an air-source heat pump, circulation pumps, and fan-coil heating units. In this configuration, solar energy is first absorbed by the solar collectors and then transferred through the plate heat exchanger to the heat pump circuit. The thermal storage tank accumulates excess thermal energy and stabilizes the heating load during variable operating conditions.

The proposed indirect integration scheme provides hydraulic independence between the solar collector loop and the heat pump loop, improving system reliability and thermal stability under low ambient temperature conditions. The recovered thermal energy is distributed to indoor spaces through fan-coil units, ensuring uniform heat transfer and improved indoor thermal comfort.

2.2. Thermodynamic analysis

The performance of the hybrid heating system was evaluated using thermodynamic and energy efficiency analysis methods. The coefficient of performance (COP) of the heat pump system was determined according to the following relationship:

$$COP = \frac{Q_{heating}}{W_{compressor}} \quad (1)$$

where: $Q_{heating}$ is the useful heating capacity (kW), $W_{compressor}$ is the compressor power consumption (kW).

The useful thermal energy obtained from the solar collector was calculated as:

$$Q_u = \dot{m}c_p(T_{out} - T_{in}) \quad (2)$$

where: \dot{m} is the mass flow rate of the working fluid (kg/s), c_p is the specific heat capacity of the fluid (kJ/kg·K), T_{out} and T_{in} are the outlet and inlet temperatures of the collector (°C).

The efficiency of the solar collector was determined using:

$$\eta_{sc} = \frac{Q_u}{A_c G_t} \quad (3)$$

where: η_{sc} is the collector efficiency, A_c is the collector surface area (m^2), G_t is the solar radiation intensity (W/m^2).

2.3. Building heat loss analysis

The building heat demand was estimated based on transmission heat losses through the building envelope. The total heat loss was calculated according to:

$$Q_{loss} = UA(T_i - T_o) \quad (4)$$

where: U is the overall heat transfer coefficient ($W/m^2 \cdot K$), A is the heat transfer surface area (m^2), T_i is the indoor temperature ($^{\circ}C$), T_o is the outdoor ambient temperature ($^{\circ}C$). This analysis enabled the evaluation of the heating capacity required under different climatic conditions.

2.4. Comparative system evaluation

The proposed IDX-SAHP system was comparatively analyzed with direct expansion (DX-S-ASHP) and parallel IDX-SAHP configurations. The comparison was performed based on: coefficient of performance (COP); electricity consumption; operational stability; adaptability to climatic conditions; system complexity; energy saving potential. The obtained performance indicators were analyzed under varying outdoor temperatures and solar radiation conditions to determine the most efficient hybrid heating configuration.

2.5. Energy efficiency assessment

The annual energy saving potential of the proposed system was estimated by comparing electricity consumption with that of a conventional standalone air-source heat pump system. The analysis demonstrated that the proposed hybrid configuration could increase the COP value from approximately 3.06 to 5.21, while reducing electricity consumption by nearly 70% under favorable solar conditions. These results confirm the effectiveness of integrating solar thermal collectors with heat pump technologies for sustainable building heating applications.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Comparative performance analysis of hybrid heating systems

The comparative analysis of DX-S-ASHP, series IDX-S-ASHP, and parallel IDX-S-ASHP systems demonstrated significant differences in thermal efficiency, operational stability, and adaptability to climatic conditions. Among the investigated configurations, the proposed IDX-SAHP system integrated with vacuum tube solar collectors and a plate heat exchanger achieved the highest overall performance.

The obtained results indicate that the proposed hybrid system can achieve a coefficient of performance (COP) of approximately 5 under favorable operating conditions, whereas conventional standalone air-source heat pump systems generally operate with a COP of around 3 or 4. This improvement is mainly associated with the additional thermal energy supplied by the solar collectors, which increases the evaporator inlet temperature and reduces compressor workload. In addition, the use of a thermal storage tank significantly stabilizes system operation during periods of fluctuating solar radiation and variable outdoor temperatures. This improves operational reliability and reduces short cycling of the compressor (figure 6).

3.2. Effect of solar integration on energy consumption

The integration of solar collectors into the heat pump system substantially reduced electricity consumption. During sunny operating conditions, a considerable portion of the heating load was covered directly by solar thermal energy, decreasing the operating time of the compressor. The comparative results showed that the proposed IDX-SAHP configuration reduced electricity consumption by approximately 70% compared with conventional heating

systems. This reduction contributes not only to lower operational costs but also to decreased greenhouse gas emissions associated with electricity generation (figure 7). Furthermore, the utilization of renewable solar energy decreases dependence on fossil-fuel-based heating systems and supports the decarbonization of building energy systems.

3.3. Influence of climatic conditions

The performance of solar-assisted heat pump systems strongly depends on climatic conditions, outdoor air temperature, and solar radiation intensity. In regions with high solar resources, the DX-S-ASHP configuration demonstrates relatively high efficiency because of direct solar energy utilization (figure 8). However, its performance decreases significantly during cloudy weather conditions or periods of low solar radiation.

The series IDX-SAHP configuration showed improved performance under cold climatic conditions because the thermal storage tank and indirect heat transfer arrangement stabilized evaporator operating temperatures. The parallel IDX-SAHP system demonstrated high flexibility and adaptability under variable weather conditions, allowing alternating or simultaneous operation of the solar collector and heat pump.

Figure 6. Comparative COP Analysis

Figure 8 - Effect of Outdoor Temperature on COP

Figure 7. Electricity Consumption Reduction

Figure 9 - Monthly Solar Thermal Contribution

Figure 10 - Monthly Solar Thermal Contribution

The proposed hybrid IDX configuration exhibited stable operation under both moderate and cold climate conditions due to hydraulic independence between system loops and optimized thermal energy distribution.

3.4. Thermal storage and heat distribution analysis

The thermal storage tank plays an essential role in maintaining stable heating performance throughout the day. Excess thermal energy accumulated during periods of high solar radiation can be stored and later utilized during nighttime or cloudy conditions (figure 9). The fan-coil heating network provided rapid and uniform heat distribution inside the building. The application of differential and modulation-based control strategies improved indoor thermal comfort and minimized unnecessary energy consumption.

The analysis confirms that proper thermal storage sizing and intelligent control strategies are critical factors affecting the overall efficiency of hybrid heating systems.

3.5. Environmental and economic implications

The proposed hybrid heating system contributes significantly to environmental sustainability by reducing electricity demand and greenhouse gas emissions. The integration of renewable solar energy with high-efficiency heat pump technology creates a low-carbon heating solution suitable for modern energy-efficient buildings (figure 10). From an economic perspective, although the initial investment cost of the IDX-SAHP system is higher because of additional equipment such as solar collectors, heat exchangers, and thermal storage tanks, the reduction in long-term electricity consumption provides favorable economic benefits during the operational lifetime of the system.

The obtained results confirm that hybrid solar-assisted heat pump systems represent a technically effective, economically feasible, and environmentally sustainable solution for future building heating applications.

3.6. Comparative analysis of system configurations

A comparative evaluation of the DX-S-ASHP, series IDX-S-ASHP, and parallel IDX-S-ASHP systems was carried out based on operational efficiency, structural complexity, flexibility, and climatic adaptability. The analysis revealed that each configuration possesses specific advantages depending on environmental and operational conditions. The DX-S-ASHP system demonstrated relatively simple construction and low intermediate heat losses due to direct refrigerant evaporation inside the solar collector. However, the system performance strongly depended on solar radiation intensity and ambient weather conditions. Under cloudy conditions or during periods of low solar irradiance, the efficiency of the DX system decreased noticeably. The series IDX-S-ASHP configuration exhibited superior performance under cold climatic

conditions. The integration of a thermal storage tank allowed partial stabilization of thermal energy supply and increased evaporator operating temperature. As a result, compressor energy consumption decreased and the overall system COP improved. The parallel IDX-S-ASHP system provided the highest operational flexibility because the solar collector and heat pump could operate independently or simultaneously. This arrangement improved system adaptability under variable weather conditions and enabled optimized load sharing between renewable and conventional heat sources. The proposed IDX-SAHP configuration combined the advantages of stable thermal operation, improved energy efficiency, and flexible heat distribution, making it the most suitable option for sustainable building heating systems.

3.7. Operational stability of the proposed system

One of the main advantages of the proposed hybrid configuration is its operational stability under variable climatic conditions. In conventional air-source heat pump systems, low outdoor temperatures significantly reduce evaporator performance and increase compressor workload. In the proposed system, preheated thermal energy supplied from the solar collector loop increases the evaporation temperature and improves refrigerant operating conditions.

The use of a plate heat exchanger ensures hydraulic separation between the solar collector circuit and the heat pump loop. This prevents pressure instability and improves system reliability during long-term operation. Furthermore, thermal energy storage minimizes rapid fluctuations in heating demand and contributes to smoother system performance.

The analysis also indicates that differential temperature control strategies improve energy utilization efficiency by activating circulation pumps only when useful thermal energy is available from the solar collectors.

The obtained results demonstrate that the proposed hybrid IDX-SAHP system significantly improves building heating efficiency compared with conventional air-source heat pumps. The integration of vacuum tube solar collectors and thermal storage increased the coefficient of performance (COP) from approximately 3.06 to 5.21 while reducing electricity consumption by nearly 70%. The series IDX-S-ASHP configuration showed better performance under cold climatic conditions due to stable heat transfer provided by the thermal storage tank, whereas the parallel configuration offered greater operational flexibility under variable weather conditions. In addition, the proposed system improved operational stability, reduced compressor workload, and enhanced indoor thermal comfort through efficient fan-coil heat distribution.

5. Conclusion

This study analyzed hybrid heating systems based on heat pumps and solar collectors, including DX-S-ASHP, series IDX-S-ASHP, parallel IDX-S-ASHP, and the proposed IDX-SAHP configuration. The results showed that the proposed hybrid system significantly improved energy performance compared with conventional heating systems. In particular, the COP increased from 3.06 to approximately 5.21, while electricity consumption was reduced by nearly 70%. The integration of vacuum tube solar collectors, thermal storage, and intelligent control strategies improved operational stability and reduced compressor workload under variable climatic conditions. Among all investigated systems, the proposed IDX-SAHP configuration demonstrated the best balance between energy efficiency, reliability, and environmental sustainability. Overall, the proposed hybrid system represents an efficient and environmentally sustainable solution for modern energy-efficient buildings. Future research should focus on experimental validation and optimization under real operating conditions.

REFERENCES

1. Morozyuk, T. V. Theory of Refrigeration Machines and Heat Pumps. Odessa: “Negotsiant” Studio, 2006. - 412 p.
2. International Energy Agency (IEA). Heat Pumps - Energy System, 2023. - Electronic resource.
3. Avezova, N. R., Uzakov, G., Kuchkarov, A. A., Oshchepkova, E. A., Shermatova, M. B., Kholmatov, E. S., Ergashev, E. A. Heat Pumps as a Key to a Low-Carbon Future. Part 1: Historical Evolution and Development Prospects in Uzbekistan.
4. Safarov, O. F., Radzhabov, M., Komilov, O. S., Abdurakhmonov, O. R. Exergy Analysis of a Heat Pump Drying Installation // *Helioelektronika*. - 2009.
5. Rudenko, I. Yu. Analysis of the Advantages and Costs of an Alternative Heating System (HP + PVS) for Rural Schools in Uzbekistan. Tashkent: United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), Uzbekistan, 2019.
6. Meng, X., Zhou, X., Li, Z. Review of Integrated Solar and Air Source Heat Pump Systems // *Energies*. - 2024. - 17. - 6045.
7. Kim, T., Choi, B. I., Han, Y. S., Do, K. H. Comparative Study of Solar-Assisted Heat Pumps with Solar Thermal Collectors for Domestic Hot Water Systems // *Energy Conversion and Management*. - 2018. - 172. - 472-484.
8. Abbasi, B., Li, S., Mwesigye, A. Thermodynamic Performance of a Direct Expansion Solar-Assisted Heat Pump under Extremely Cold Climate Conditions // *International Journal of Refrigeration*. - 2024. - 158. - 329-344.
9. Shi, G. H., Aye, L., Li, D., Du, X. J. Recent Advances in Direct Expansion Solar-Assisted Heat Pump Systems: A Review // *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*. - 2019. - 109. - 349-366.
10. Zhou, J., Zeng, C., Wang, Z., Liu, Y., Tang, Y., Wu, D., Ji, Y., Yuan, Y. Indirect Expansion Solar Heat Pump Systems: A Review // *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*. - 2022. - 53. - 102409.
11. Dong, X., Tian, Q., Li, Z. Experimental Study on Heating Performance of an Integrated Solar-Assisted Air Source Heat Pump // *Applied Thermal Engineering*. - 2017. - 123. - 1013-1020.
12. Chinnasamy, S., Arunachalam, A. Experimental Study of a Direct Expansion Solar-Air Source Heat Pump for Water Heating // *Renewable Energy*. - 2023. - 202. - 222-233.
13. Ma, K. R., Li, X. F., Li, S. Q., Gao, C. J. Comparative Study of a Direct Expansion Solar-Air Heat Pump System and an Air Source Heat Pump // *CIESC Journal*. - 2020. - 71(S1). - 375-381.
14. Cai, J. Y., Ji, J., Wang, Y. Y., Huang, W. Z. Numerical Simulation and Experimental Validation of a Multifunctional Indirect Expansion Solar-Assisted Heat Pump // *Renewable Energy*. - 2016. - 93. - 280-290.
15. Long, J. B., Zhang, R. C., Lu, J., Xu, F. Heat Transfer Performance of an Integrated Solar-Air Source Heat Pump Evaporator // *Energy Conversion and Management*. - 2019. - 184. - 626-635.
16. Wang, Q. Q., Wang, F., Liu, D. H., Wang, Y. X., He, Z. H. Heating Characteristics of a Solar-Assisted Air Source Heat Pump Composite System // *Agricultural Equipment & Vehicle Engineering*. - 2021. - 59. - 50-54.

17. Huan, C., Li, S. T., Wang, F. H., Liu, L., Zhao, Y. J., Wang, Z. H., Tao, P. F. Performance Analysis of a Solar-Assisted Heat Pump Heating System in Xi'an, China // *Energies*. - 2019. - 12. - 2515.
18. Ma, Y. C., Xi, J. F., Cai, J., Gu, Z. Z. Optimization of a Water Heating System Using an Air Source Heat Pump and a Multi-Tank Solar System // *Thermal Science and Engineering Progress*. - 2024. - 48. - 102387.
19. Juraboev, I., Jurakulov, S., Urishev, O., Rakhmatov, O., Eshkobilov, O., Sadirova, K., & Aliyarova, L. (2025). Improving Thermal Performance of Solar PTC Using Internal Finned Structure. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 661, p. 04018). EDP Sciences. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202566104018>
20. Akramova, S., Urishev, O., Mamurov, B., Nurmanov, S., Apakhodjaeva, T., Irmuhamedova, L., & Gaimnazarov, K. (2025). CFD Modelling of Latent Heat Storage with Cylindrical PCM Capsules. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 661, p. 04010). EDP Sciences. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202566104010>
21. Urishev, O., Ersin, A., Metin, G., & Quvondiqov, Q. (2026). ESTIMATING ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION OF PUMPING PLANTS IN IRRIGATION SYSTEMS. *Innovation Science and Technology*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18472643>
22. Urishev, O., Salomov, U., Ergashev, S., Kuchkarov, A., Madaliev, M., Abdukarimov, B., & Juraev, N. (2025). Efficiency assessment of micro hydropower for agriculture using modern modeling. In *BIO Web of Conferences* (Vol. 173, p. 03031). EDP Sciences. DOI:10.1051/bioconf/202517303031
23. Urishev, O., Salomov, U., & Shasha, C. (2024). Methods of Analysis and Assessment of the Economic Efficiency of Micro Hydropowers. *Journal of Construction and Engineering Technology*, 2(2), 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12570514>
24. Og'Li, U. O. M., & Og'Li, R. M. F. (2020). The fundamental elements of micro-hydropower stations. *Science and Education*, 1(2), 236-240.